

Study on Effects of Mordants on Dyeing of Cotton using Tesu Flower Natural Dye

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Abstract:

This research paper deals with the use of natural dye made from Tesu flower extract to colour cotton cloth. This study involves extracting the dye from the petals of the tesu flower, dyeing cotton fabric with alum, ferrous sulphate, and myrobalan (harda) mordant, and then assessing the fastness properties and colour strength of dyed fabric samples. Extraction, pre-mordanting, and dyeing of cotton fabric using an aqueous extract of Tesu flower petals using various types of mordants was carried out to observe the impact on the dyed fabric's colour strength and fastness characteristics. In this paper, the effect of premordanting on colour strength and fastness properties was studied.

Keywords: colour strength, fastness properties, mordants, natural dye, Tesu flower

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1. Introduction

Since natural dyes are more expensive and harder to obtain, they aren't as commonly employed in industries as synthetic dyes despite being the environmentally safest option. But, one of the major drawback of synthetic dyes is that they are made from petrochemical sources using hazardous chemical procedures and they pose a threat to environmental sustainability [1-2]. Plant parts that contain tannin, flavonoids, quinonoid, etc. are used to extract natural dyes. Examples of these parts include bark (e.g., purple bark, Sappan wood, Shillicorai, Khair, Red, and Sandalwood), leaves (e.g., Indigo, Henna, Eucalyptus, Tea, Cardamon, Coral Jasmine, Lemon Grass), roots (e.g., Turmeric, Madder, Onions, Beet-root), fruits or seeds (e.g., Latkan, pomegranate rind, Beetle nut, Myrobalan), and flowers (e.g. Marigold, Dahlia, Tesu, Kusum) [3]. The colour and fibre being used determine which mordant is best in the context of colour strength and fastness properties. Various mordants react differently with different natural dyes. [4-6] The ability of a dyed or printed material to retain its colour against different external influences, such light, washing, rubbing, perspiration, etc., is known as colour fastness. It gauges how long a colour will last before fading, bleeding, or spreading to adjacent surfaces. Since colour fastness affects how long and durable a colour will last in textiles, it is a crucial quality factor. A variety of tests are performed to evaluate a dyed textile material's colour fastness [7-9]. Light fastness, washing fastness, rubbing fastness and perspiration fastness are the most common tests. Numerous procedures, such as optimal dye selection, pre-treatments, the use of suitable mordants or fixing agents, and optimised dyeing or printing methods, can lead to improved colour fastness.[10-12]. This paper is a step towards understanding the effect of premordanting on colour strength and fastness properties of cotton fabric dyed with Tesu flower natural dye.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Materials

100% cotton fabric, procured from local market, was used in this study. The purity of the fabric is confirmed through solubility and burning test. Laboratory Grade reagents like alum, ferrous sulphate and myrobalan (Hardan) was used as mordanting agent. Tesu flower (*Butea Monosperma*) also known as Flame of the Forest, was used for dye extraction. LR grade Sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) was used in dyeing for pH adjustment, dye fixation, enhanced dye solubility and dye levelling. Common salt (NaCl) was used as for enhancing the affinity of the dye towards the fabric. Turkey red oil (TRO) was used to reduce surface tension which results in reduction of time of the dyeing process and consequently its energy consumption, and thus reduces the amount of effluent generated while improving hydrophilicity and fastness properties.

2.2 Fabric Specification

Fabric Type	Cotton Fabric
Conformity Test	Test Procedure
Burning test	Burning test was done to check for 100% cotton. Fabric burnt with paper like smell and forms grey ash.
Solubility test	Warp and weft yarns from the fabric was taken and dissolved in 75% H ₂ SO ₄ solution and kept for 30 mins. The yarns were completely dissolved in solution thus validating the fabric is 100% cotton.

Fabric Type	Specifications
100% cotton Fabric	Warp count – 16.49 Ne
	Weft count – 22.14 Ne
	EPI- 128
	PPI- 96
	GSM – 157 g/m ²

2.3 Machines

i. Water bath

A water bath is a scientific equipment used to maintain a steady temperature for a prolonged time when incubating samples. It is employed to enable some chemical reactions at high temperatures. A big container filled with warm water makes up a hot water bath. A laboratory water bath's container capacity ranges from 12 to 32 litres for a standard model and 50 to 100 litres for a large water bath.

ii. HTHP dyeing machine

HTHP (High-Temperature High-Pressure) dyeing machines are specialized dyeing equipment used in textile dyeing processes. These machines are used for dyeing at elevated temperatures and under high pressure, which helps in achieving faster and more uniform dye absorption by the fibres.

iii. Visible Spectrophotometer

A spectrophotometer is a device commonly used in color measurement and analysis. It measures the intensity of light at different wavelengths, allowing for the characterization of the spectral properties of an object or a sample's color.

iv. Launder-o-meter

Washing Fastness Tester (Launder-o-meter), is used to determine color fastness to washing. The washing fastness tester uses stainless steel rotor to holds washpots on each of four sides and rotates at a constant 40 rpm (+/-2 rpm). Washpots are preheated in appropriate test solution.

v. Crock meter

Crock meter is an instrument used to determine color fastness to wet and dry rubbing.

2.4 Methods

Extraction Process

The Tesu flower was plucked manually at its blooming season (spring season). The petals are separated from flower and kept under sun for 2-3 days until they got completely dried. Further the dried petals are grinded in dry mixer grinder and made into fine powder. Tesu powder, prepared after grinding the sun-dried petals of palash flower, was taken in hot water for extraction of its color component under such conditions i.e. time 60 min, temperature 90°C, MLR 1:20 and pH 11. Detail recipe of Tesu dye extraction process is shown in the table 1.

Table 1: Detail recipe for Tesu dye extraction process

S. No.	Component	Quantity
1	Dye Source (Tesu Powder)	4 g
2	Extraction Medium (RO Water)	80 ml
3	Material to Liquor Ratio	1:20
4	Temperature	90°C
5	Time	60 Min
6	pH	11

Pre - Mordanting Process

In this process silk is pre mordanted with different mordants (1% OWF) viz. alum, ferrous sulphate and myrobalan (Harda) in a water bath at 100°C for 30 minutes in aqueous medium. Mordanted fabric samples were finally dried in air without washing to make them ready for subsequent dyeing.

Dyeing Process

Dried pre-mordanted cotton fabric samples is put in the extracted dye solution kept in dye pot. Common salt & sodium carbonate was added to improve and facilitate dyeing process. Dye pots ware then placed in HTHP dyeing machine for 60 min at 90°C. Detail recipe for dyeing cotton fabric samples is shown in the table 2.

Table 2: Detail recipe for dyeing cotton fabric samples

S. No.	Component	Particular
1	Fabric samples	100% cotton
2	Dyeing Medium	water
3	Material to Liquor Ratio	1:40
4	Temperature	90°C
5	Time	60 Min
6	pH	11

The dyed cotton fabric samples were washed with cold water and then dried. K/S value of dyed cotton samples were tested for colour strength in spectrophotometer (Model – SS5100A) in reflectance mode. The value of colour strength (K/S value) of the cotton fabric samples was measured through the well-known Kubelka – Munk theory. The theory shows the relationship between reflectance (R), scattering (S) and its light absorption (K) which are given below in equation (1):

Colour strength (K/S) = $(1-R)^2/2R$ (1).

Colour fastness tests

The colour fastness of dyed cotton sample with respect to washing and rubbing were measured.

Washing fastness

The washing fastness of dyed cotton fabric samples were measured as per the IS/ISO 105 C01 A1:2006 specifications. The testing method is as follows:

The washing fastness was tested using Launder-o-meter of AATCC. It consists of a water bath which rotates the shafts at 40±2 rpm. A layer of dyed fabric (10 cm×4 cm) was sewed between cotton and polyester fabric samples. The specimen was treated with 5 g/l standard soap (containing not more than 5% moisture) at 40°C for 30 minutes. The material to liquor ratio is 1:50. After treatment, the composite is rinsed twice in cold distilled water and then with cold running water for 10 minutes and then squeezed. The composite specimen is opened out by removing stitches from all sides except one shorter side. It is then dried at a temperature lower than 60°C. The change in colour in the samples was assessed by Grey Scale.

Rubbing fastness

Dry and wet rubbing fastness of the dyed cotton fabric samples were tested using a crock meter as per Indian Standard IS 766:1988 (Reaffirmed 2004) based on ISO 105-X12:2001. The crock meter has a finger of 1.6 meter diameter which can move two and fro in a straight 10 cm track on the specimen. The rubbing is carried out by

moving 10 times in 10 seconds with a downward force of 6 N. Undyed unfinished cloth is cut into pieces of 5×5 sq. cm and placed on the finger. Two pair of specimens not less than 14×5 sq. cm are cut. One pair is for dry rubbing test and one for wet rubbing test. In wet rubbing test, the rubbing cloth is wetted and squeezed until it contains its own weight of water. The staining of the rubbing cloth is assessed by Grey Scale.

3. Result and discussion

Effect of three different mordants on colour strength (k/s value) of cotton fabric.

The colour strength (K/S value) of cotton fabric dyed with Tesu flower dye using three different mordants viz. alum, ferrous sulphate and Harda after applying pre-mordanting methods is shown in table 3 and fig 1.

Table 3: Colour strength (k/s value) of cotton fabric dyed with Tesu flower dye with three different mordants

Mordant	Mean k/s Value
Without Mordant	51.571
Alum	45.073
Ferrous sulphate	74.89
Myrobalan (Harda)	70.504

Figure 1: Colour strength (K/S value) of cotton fabric dyed with Tesu flower dye with three different mordants

Figure 1 explains the effect of different mordants on the colour strength (K/S value) of cotton fabric. It was observed that when cotton fabric samples dyed with Tesu flower dye with three different mordants, colour strength (K/S value) of the dyed cotton fabric sample using ferrous sulphate as a mordant shows maximum colour yield followed by the fabric samples dyed with Tesu flower dye with harda then without mordant and then with alum.

Effect of three different mordants on washing fastness of dyed cotton fabric

For washing fastness naturally dyed fabrics are softly handled so they are washed in mild soap solution with 5gpl for 30min. at 40 + 2 without putting steel balls. First cut sample of dyed fabrics, cotton fabric & PC fabric of same fabric. Stitch them together. Prepare washing bath solution with 5 gpl of detergent in 1 Liter water. Keep samples in mild washing solution for 30min. at 40°C and then dry them. Rating of washing fastness was measured by visible spectrophotometer and was given on the basis of AATCC Evaluation Procedure 7/ ISO 105 – A05 and is depicted in the table no. 4 and fig 2.

Table 4. Washing fastness rating of cotton fabric dyed with Tesu flower dye using three different mordant

S. No.	Type of mordant	Rating	Remark
1	Without Mordant	2	Average
2	Alum	1 – 2	Poor to average
3	Ferrous sulphate	3	Good
4	Myrobalan (Harda)	2	Average

Figure 2: Washing fastness rating of cotton fabric dyed with Tesu flower dye using three different mordant

Figure 2 explains the effect of different mordants on the washing fastness properties of cotton fabric. It was observed that when cotton fabric samples dyed with Tesu flower dye with three different mordants one by one, washing fastness properties of the cotton fabric sample using Ferrous sulphate as a mordant shows maximum washing fastness rating followed by the fabric samples dyed with Tesu flower dye without mordant and with harda and alum mordant.

Effect of three different mordants on rubbing fastness (Dry and Wet) of dyed cotton fabric

For rubbing fastness naturally dyed fabrics was cut into appropriate sizes, typically 10 cm x 4 cm. 10 number of strokes are performed at the specified pressure. After completing the rubbing process, the fabric sample was carefully removed from the crock meter. Rating of rubbing fastness was given on the basis of the standard of staining scale AATCC evaluation procedure 12/ISO 105 – A034 and is depicted in the table no. 5 and fig 3.

Table 5. Rubbing fastness (Dry and Wet) rating of cotton fabric dyed with Tesu flower dye using three different mordant

S. No.	Mordant used	Rubbing fastness - Dry	Rubbing fastness - wet
1	Without Mordant	4-5	1-2
2	Alum	4-5	1-2
3	Ferrous sulphate	5	2-3
4	Myrobalan (Harda)	2-3	1

Figure 3: Rubbing fastness (Dry and Wet) rating of cotton fabric dyed with Tesu flower dye using three different mordant

Figure 3 explains the effect of different mordants on the rubbing fastness (dry and wet) properties of cotton fabric. It was observed that when cotton fabric samples dyed with Tesu flower dye with three different mordants one by one, rubbing fastness (dry and wet) properties of the cotton fabric sample using Ferrous sulphate as a mordant shows maximum washing fastness rating followed by the fabric samples dyed with Tesu flower dye without mordant and with alum mordant and harda. Overall dry rubbing fastness is better than the corresponding wet rubbing fastness properties of the dyed cotton fabric.

4. Conclusion

Different mordants have the significant influence of the colour yield of dyed cotton fabric dyed with Tesu flower dye extracts. Out of all the three mordant used ferrous sulphate mordant shows maximum colour yield followed by the fabric samples dyed with Tesu flower dye without mordant and with alum mordant and harda. As far as fastness properties are concerns, washing fastness properties of the cotton fabric sample using Ferrous sulphate as a mordant shows maximum washing fastness rating followed by the fabric samples dyed with Tesu flower dye with harda then without mordant and then with alum and for rubbing fastness properties (dry and wet) Ferrous sulphate as a mordant shows maximum rubbing fastness rating followed by the fabric samples dyed with Tesu flower dye without mordant and with alum mordant and harda. Overall dry rubbing fastness is better than the corresponding wet rubbing fastness properties of the dyed cotton fabric.

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